

Perspectives in Software Engineering Research: Insights through the SE 2026 Lens

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"From AI and cybersecurity to sustainability and healthcare, advances in software are driving innovation across all sectors of modern industry and society". This is how the newly established Informatics Europe Working Group on Software Research¹ emphasises *software* as one of the pillars underpinning Europe's digital future, and therefore characterises *software engineering* as "the enabling technology and invisible infrastructure of the digital age" [Vos 2026].

At the same time, software engineering itself is undergoing profound transformation. Disruptive technologies such as Generative AI and quantum computing, increasing concerns about digital sovereignty, growing sustainability requirements, the ever-accelerating pace of software construction itself, the continuously increasing complexity of the constructed software-intensive systems, and many other driving forces are reshaping the discipline.

So, what are the current trends and perspectives in software engineering research in this period of transformation? There are certainly many answers and controversial discussions to this question. In this article, we take a brief and selective look at this question through the lens of the annual Software Engineering (SE) conference of the Software Engineering Division (SWT) of the German Informatics Society (GI)², organised in cooperation with the Swiss Informatics Society (SI) and the Austrian Computer Society (OCG). This year's edition, SE

2026³, recently took place from 23–27 February in Bern, Switzerland, hosting around 250 participants from both academia and software engineering practice.

Scientific Program

The scientific program of the SE conference presented significant contributions to software engineering research that were accepted or published within the last two years at renowned international conferences or in leading journals. This year, there were 80 submissions for the main program, of which 64 were accepted with summaries published in the conference proceedings [Kehrer 2026]; the original publications are distributed across international software engineering venues as follows:

The SE 2026 conference program strongly reflected the ongoing paradigm shift towards "AI-first software engineering". Large Language Models (LLMs) and GenAI were touched across virtually all software engineering activities, from requirements engineering over software

¹ <https://www.informatics-europe.org/research/software-research.html>

² <https://fb-swt.gi.de/>

³ <https://se2026.inf.unibe.ch/en/>

construction to software analysis. In all of these activities, the research focus is no longer solely on the explorative usage of AI techniques and tools but also on understanding their reliability, explainability, risks, and integration into real-world development workflows.

At the same time, the program also demonstrated the continued importance of classical software engineering topics. For example, formal verification, software architecture, variability management, and empirical software engineering remained strongly represented. We do not see this as a contradiction, as these areas continue to provide the methodological foundations required to build trustworthy, reliable, and maintainable systems, including those comprising AI components, those developed using AI-centric methods and tools, or both.

In sum, the scientific program of SE 2026 did not reflect a replacement of classical software engineering, but rather a convergence in which AI-centric approaches increasingly build upon and extend traditional software engineering foundations. This is in line with one of the grand challenges of computer science identified by the German Informatics Society (GI) in 2025⁴.

Scientific Keynotes

The scientific program also featured two keynote talks, both of which reflected the interplay between AI and software engineering, though the main focus of this interplay was, arguably, on different directions, typically framed as "AI4SE" and "SE4AI", respectively:

"AI4SE": In his keynote entitled "Towards Human-like Software Testing" [Chen 2026], Chunyang Chen emphasised the importance of considering how software is actually used and assessed by humans when designing automated testing approaches. He presented several studies in which human-like testing was performed

using LLM-driven testing agents, particularly for GUI testing of mobile applications. The goal of this human-centric testing approach is to explore AI-centric strategies, constraints, and intentions that more closely resemble those of end users.

"SE4AI": In her keynote entitled "Systematic Testing for Complex Systems in the Absence of Oracles" [Christakis 2026], Maria Christakis focused on metamorphic testing as a unifying foundation for testing complex systems in the absence of traditional test oracles. She demonstrated how metamorphic testing can uncover soundness and precision bugs in a variety of domains, including program analysers, cryptographic proof systems, and machine-learning models whose behaviour is based on learned representations. Her keynote illustrated how established verification principles continue to evolve towards new application domains shaped by AI and data-driven systems.

Co-located Events

The symbiosis between emerging paradigms and established software engineering foundations was also visible in the co-located events.

The 2026 CHOOSE Forum⁵, organised by the Swiss (CH) Group for Original and Outside-the-box Software Engineering of the Swiss Informatics Society (SI), brought together experts from software engineering, artificial intelligence, and other scientific disciplines to explore the evolving intersections of these fields. Similarly, the SEUH⁶ conference ("Software Engineering im Unterricht der Hochschulen") on software engineering education in the higher education sector, focused strongly on the impact of AI on teaching and learning. The SEUH participants interactively explored and discussed open questions related to programming education with and without AI support, software engineering education in the age of AI, and the opportunities and challenges of

⁴ <https://gi.de/grand-challenges/vollautomatisierte-software-entwicklung>

⁵ <https://choose.swissinformatics.org/events/choose-forum-2026-software-engineering-ai-scientific-computing/>
⁶ <https://www.seuh.org/seuh2026/>

AI-based tutoring systems in software engineering education.

The industry day⁷, dedicated to the topic of digital sovereignty, critically examined the tension between dependence on AI providers and cloud infrastructures on the one hand, and maintaining control over training data, models, and infrastructures on the other. In her industry keynote entitled “Achieving Digital Sovereignty in Europe: Key Considerations for Success”⁸, Amandine Le Pape, co-founder of Matrix/Element, reflected on the very concept of digital sovereignty, its growing importance, and the central role of open source and digital commons in achieving it. She also discussed potential pitfalls and shared best practices for successfully implementing digital sovereignty initiatives.

A similar picture was drawn by the seven accepted workshops⁹, which together reflected both continuity and disruption within software engineering. On the one hand, highly established workshops represented long-standing software engineering domains, particularly in the German-speaking region. A prominent example is the 23rd edition of the Automotive Software Engineering workshop (ASE'26), where traditional concerns such as safety and security remained central, but also topics such as automated driving, cloud connectivity, and voice interaction highlighted the shift towards increasingly data-driven and AI-enabled software systems. On the other hand, several historically younger workshops focused explicitly on disruptive technologies and emerging paradigms, such as the 3rd Workshop on Generative and Neurosymbolic AI in Software Engineering (GenSE'26) and the 3rd International Workshop on Quantum Software

Engineering Tools, Algorithms & Verification (Q-STAV'26).

Finally, the Software Engineering Division of the GI presented an award for the best PhD thesis¹⁰. Furthermore, as part of the student research competition¹¹, prizes were awarded to the best bachelor's and master's theses in software engineering. The excellent works that were nominated for presentation and awarded prizes covered a wide range of topics, demonstrating how young researchers are addressing current challenges and becoming integrated within the SE research community. With research topics ranging from neural bug detection to functional modelling of cyber-physical systems, it is particularly noteworthy that the early-career researchers' contributions reflect the current trends and perspectives within the community: The convergence of classical SE foundations with AI-driven and data-driven approaches, and the remarkable breadth of contemporary software engineering research.

Conclusion and Outlook

Overall, the SE 2026 conference program showcased a software engineering community undergoing a major paradigm shift while building on rigorous software engineering foundations. In particular, GenAI is no longer treated as an experimental topic, but has become deeply integrated into research. At the same time, the field continues to rely on its traditional foundations, such as formal modelling and analysis as well as empirical evaluation.

Looking ahead, the software engineering community will increasingly face the challenge of combining the productivity gains of AI-based development with the rigour required for engineering dependable and trustworthy modern software systems. We believe that this

⁷ <https://se2026.inf.unibe.ch/en/tracks/industry-day/>

⁸ <https://se2026.inf.unibe.ch/en/program/keynotes/amandine-le-pape/>

⁹ <https://dl.gi.de/handle/20.500.12116/48241>

¹⁰ <https://se2026.inf.unibe.ch/de/tracks/dissertationspreis/>

¹¹ <https://se2026.inf.unibe.ch/de/tracks/student-research-competition/>

will require a deep understanding of how human expertise and intelligent automation can effectively complement each other. The SE conference series will continue to provide an

important forum for shaping and critically reflecting on this evolution, and the community is already looking forward to the next edition in 2027 at the Technical University of Dortmund¹².

References

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¹² <https://se2027.cs.tu-dortmund.de/>